

THE INFLUENCE OF TEACHING AND LEARNING RESOURCES ON THE INTEGRATION OF THE NATIONAL GOALS OF EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Teaching and Learning Resources refer to the materials that the classroom teacher uses to help the learners to acquire and understand knowledge, concepts, skills and attitudes that he/she introduces during his/her lesson. Teaching and learning resources include but are not limited to structural facilities like properly ventilated classrooms, furniture, kitchen, safe clean water, playground, toilets, and play grounds. Teaching and learning resources entail also instructional materials including text books (course books and supplementary books), charts, wall maps, picture books, flash cards, and real objects (*realia*), to name but a few. The general aim of this study was to examine the influence of the teaching and learning resources on the integration on the national goals of education in Early Childhood Development and Education (ECDE). Since this objective was about the relationship between the teaching/learning resources and the integration of the national goals of education, the researcher used the Spearman's Correlation Coefficient to determine whether there was a relationship between the teaching and learning resources and the integration of the national goals of education in Early Childhood Development and Education, and the strength of the relationship if it existed. The N=158 including 28 head teachers and 130 preschool teachers. The n=66 including 14 head teachers and 52 preschool teachers. The head teachers were interviewed following the guide with the following questions in the interview guide: What is the influence of the teaching and learning resources on the integration of the national goals of education? The head teachers interviewed indicated that the correlation coefficient between the teaching and learning resources and the integration of the national goals of education rates at 0.85. This shows that there is a very strong

positive (relationship) correlation between teaching and learning resources and the integration of the national goals of education. The preschool teachers responded to questions in the questionnaires. (a) The closed questions required the respondents to indicate the extent to which they agreed/disagreed on the statements given on a scale of 5-1. (b) The open ended questions required the respondents to state, on their opinion how teaching and learning resources influenced the integration of the national goals of education in Early Childhood Development and Education. The respondents indicated that the teaching and learning resources' prevalence presented a very strong positive correlation between the teaching and learning resources and the integration of the national goals of education in Early Childhood Development and Education, which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The study established that teaching and learning resources influence effective implementation of Early Childhood Development and Education programmes in preschools. A unit increase of the teaching and learning resources would lead to an increase in effective Early Childhood Development and Education by a factor of 0.702. This study recommends that Early Childhood Development and Education centers should be provided with the age appropriate, relevant, and adequate teaching and learning resources. These resources will go a long way in enhancing effective curriculum content delivery as they create a conducive learner friendly environment fully equipped with structural and instructional resources that learners can freely, actively, interestingly, variably, and creatively manipulate to generate, create and acquire knowledge, concepts, skills, and attitudes with minimal teacher guidance.

Keywords: learning resources, teaching resources, national goals of education, Kenya

1. Introduction

Early Childhood Development and Education refers to the education catering for children aged 3-6 years. Early childhood is a critical period to lay the foundation for success in education and beyond and thus early childhood care and education should be at the center of Education for All and broader Sustainable Development Goals, EFA Global Monitoring Report. The experiences during this period are known to enhance or inhibit realization of one's potentials in life (Mutinda, 2010). The way a child is nurtured spiritually, morally, socially, emotionally, intellectually and physically creates a long life learning process (United Nations Educational, Scientific and cultural Organization, 2004). Therefore, children who are nurtured well can live and create better societies for themselves and for all.

Many ECDE centers lack adequate teaching and learning resources and facilities suitable for ECDE in their learning environment. These include lack of properly ventilated classrooms, furniture suitable for children, kitchen, safe clean water, playground, toilets and play materials all which are necessities advocated for by the International Association for the Education of Young Children. This implies that teachers do not have adequate teaching and learning resources to enable them to implement ECDE Curriculum effectively. This affects implementation of ECDE Curriculum negatively as the creation of an unsustainable learning environment helps deprive children to improve their academic performance (Offenheiser & Holcombe, 2003).

According to Kasim (2008), instructional resources are very vital in the acquisition of knowledge, concepts and skills in pre-schools. Children learn by doing. They learn better by manipulating materials (hands on activities) and making sense out of them. For a long time, there has been a debate on the best time to introduce instructional resources in number work in the life of a learner. The pre-school curriculum is thus designed to include learning of number work since it has emerged that the best time to introduce instructional resources in number work to a learner is at the pre-school age ECDE Policy Guidelines (2006).

Guthrie (2012) notes that instructional materials, if used efficiently and actively facilitate the learning process in classrooms. However, the situation is not good in most pre-schools. Firstly, only the lower quality and the less quantity of instructional resources are provided to pre-schools. In this way, the availability of instructional resources is strained and very limited. Secondly, pre-school teachers are not trained for using instructional resources. Teachers do not take interest in using the instructional resources as observed by Waithaka (2005).

Kate (2012) postulates that learning of number work as a result of experience and active learner involvement in the routine use of different types of instructional resources continues to be sensual because it helps learners to connect real things and events with their abstract representations. The ability to picture and do things in their minds would be enhanced by frequent reference to real world application. It is true to say that long term use of concrete materials with pre-scholars is positively related to increase in the learner's number work achievement and improved attitudes of learners towards number work. Farrant (2011) suggests that good instructional resources need little or no explanation, stimulate ideas and demand active responses from the learners.

Waithaka (2005) emphasizes the importance of training ECDE teachers as he observes that most ECDE centers in Kenya lay emphases on academic work, giving little or no time at all for learners to interact with instructional materials. He further

observes that in Kenya pre-school children are subjected to academic work due to pressure from parents who would like to see their children read and write within weeks upon joining pre-school. The ECDE curriculum developed by Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) has the provision for learners to interact with instructional materials but this is overlooked by parents and some private schools managers who insist that the pre-school children have to be taught numeracy and literacy to have the ability to read and write. This fact is compounded by the fact that the primary school head teachers subject the ECDE children to oral and written interviews they have to pass for them to be admitted to standard one, hence giving no room for learners to interact freely with instructional resources depending on their ability and at their level of development.

2. Methodology

Ogula (2005) describes a research design as a plan, structure and strategy of investigation to obtain answers to research questions and control variance. Additionally, a study design is the plan of action the researcher adopts for answering the research questions and it sets up the framework for study or is the blueprint of the researcher (Kerlinger, 1973). This study employed a descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey research designs are used in preliminary and exploratory studies to allow researchers to gather information, summarize, present and interpret for the purpose of clarification (Orodho, 2003). Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) on the other hand give the purpose of descriptive research as determining and reporting the way things are. Borg and Gall (1989) observe that, descriptive survey research is intended to produce statistical information on aspects of education that interests policy makers and educators. The study suited within the provisions of descriptive survey research design because the researcher collected data and reported the way things were given by respondents without manipulating any variables.

3. Target Population

According to Ogula (2005), population refers to any group of institutions, people or objects that have common characteristics. The target population for this study constituted of 28 head teachers, and 130 pre-school teachers in Kalundu Zone. Therefore, the target population was 158 in total, from which the researcher carried out the sampling to get the 14 head teachers, and 52 pre-school teachers that were involved in the study.

4. Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

Sampling is a procedure, process or technique of choosing a sub-group from a population to participate in the study Ogula (2005). It is the process of selecting a number of individuals for a study in such a way that the individuals selected represent the large group from which they were selected. Simple random sampling and Purposive sampling were used to select the respondents. In a descriptive research, a sample size of 10-50% is acceptable (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). The researcher applied the sampling error formula (Creswell, 2011 pp. 609-612) to get a sample size of 66 respondents. These comprised of 14 head teachers and 52 pre-school teachers. This formed a sample size of 41.8% of the target population because the larger the sample, the better the representative of the mean and standard deviation of the target population.

Table 1: Representation of the Sampling Matrix

Population Description	Target Population	Sample Size (%)	Sample Size
Head teachers	28	50%	14
Pre-school teachers	130	40%	52
Total	158	41.8%	66

5. Data Collection Instruments

The data collection tools for this study were questionnaires and interview guides. The questionnaires were filled in by the pre-school teachers. They had open and closed questions for the respondents to record their answers. The interview guides were used for the head teachers. The researcher followed a script of questions to elicit answers from the head teachers.

5.1 Questionnaires

Questionnaires were used for the purpose of collecting primary quantitative data. Additionally, the questionnaires will be used for the following reasons: a) It has potential in reaching out to a large number of respondents within a short time, b) It is able to give the respondents adequate time to respond to the items, c) It offers a sense of anonymity to the respondent and d) It is an objective method hence no bias resulting from the personal characteristics - as in an interview (Owens, 2002). The questionnaires were divided into the main areas of investigation except the first part which captures the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Other sections were organized according to the major research objectives.

5.2 Interviews

An interview is one way of investigating a group's attitudes and opinions. The interview guides contained items covering all the objectives of the study. The researcher used semi-structured interviews to obtain data on head teachers' views and opinions.

5.3 Pilot Study

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), a pilot study with a sample of a tenth of the total sample with homogenous characteristics is appropriate for the pilot study. Pilot study was carried out in the neighboring Kitui West Sub-County.

5.4 Validity of the Research Instruments

Validity refers to the degree to which evidence and theory support the interpretation of test scores entailed by use of tests. The validity of instrument is the extent to which it does measure what it is supposed to measure. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (1999), validity is the accuracy and meaningfulness of inferences, which are based on the research results.

5.5 Reliability of the Research Instruments

The researcher measured the reliability of the questionnaire to determine its consistency in testing what they are intended to measure. The test re-test technique was used to estimate the reliability of the instruments. This involved administering the same test twice to the same group of respondents who had been identified for this purpose.

5.6 Data Collection Procedure

Prior to the commencement of data collection, the researcher obtained all the necessary documents, including an introduction letter from the University and a research permit was obtained from the National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI).

5.7 Data Analysis

On receipt of the completed questionnaires, the collected data was checked for errors in responses, omissions, exaggerations and biases. The researcher used both the quantitative and the qualitative analysis of the data obtained from the study. Content analysis technique was used to analyze qualitative data collected using interview schedules and reported in narrative form along with quantitative presentation. The researcher used summary tables to describe the qualitative data (APA 2010). The answers/responses given in the interviews were categorized into their particular types

and the numbers of each type were counted up. In this way, the researcher converted qualitative data into quantitative data or nominal data Creswell, (2011). The qualitative data was used to reinforce the quantitative data. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were used to describe the data and for this reason, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 was used. Analysis of Variance was used to test the level of significance of the variables on the dependent variable at 95% confidence level. In addition, the study conducted a multiple regression analysis.

The regression equation was:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \epsilon$$

Whereby

Y = Early Childhood Development Education;

X1 = Financial Resources;

X2 = Teaching and Learning Resources;

X3 = Socio-Economic Factors;

X4 = Teacher-Child Ratio

β_1 , β_2 , β_3 and β_4 are coefficients of determination

ϵ is the error term.

6. Conclusion

The study concluded that teaching and learning resources have a positive influence on the integration of national goals of education in early childhood education program. The study also concluded that if the government can provide high quality instructional resources, put more emphasis on instructional materials rather than academic and provide enough school playground, toilets and play material can lead to effective integration of national goals of education in early childhood education program.

6.1 Recommendation

The study recommends that all ECDE centers should be provided with adequate teaching and learning resource and facilities suitable for ECDE in their learning environment. These include proper ventilated classrooms, furniture suitable for children, kitchen, safe clean water, playground, toilets, and play materials among others.

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